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Lead Exposure in Law Enforcement Using Novel Tasers: A Pilot Study

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KEYWORDS

Lead;
Heavy Metal;
Shooting Range;
Novel Tasers.

ABSTRACT

Evaluation of hazards associated with Conductive Electrical Weapons (CEWs) (aka tasers) has focused on the physiological effects of electrical shock and not heavy metal exposure. Gun ranges have long been recognized as sources of lead exposure. When evaluating heavy metal exposure on firing ranges, often components of firearms like lead primers or lead ammunition are identified as the primary sources of lead. This paper serves to identify another potential heavy metal hazard at training centers which are employed by law enforcement or military. Novel Taser cartridges can carry similar components of firearm propellants, including lead primer. Many tasers are not considered firearms by class because they use compressed nitrogen gas as the propellant, but this paper aims to create a call to action to study Novel Tasers. Novel Tasers are considered firearms because they use gun powder to propel projectiles and fall under the definition of “firearm” due to the explosive nature of the gunpowder (A.T.F., 2017). Industrial hygiene sampling was performed to test if taser cartridges created a lead hazard to cadets and/or trainers during law enforcement academy certifications. The trainers fired close to 90 rounds to simulate training day where around 100 rounds are fired throughout the day. Lead surface samples were taken from various objects within the training center. The highest level of lead was found on a trainer’s keyboard at 47.0 µg/ft². The other detectable levels of lead were found on the grappling mats in the room where the Novel Taser was fired with three samples having 28.9 µg/ft², 7.0 ug/ft² and 1.9 µg/ft². This study reveals the presence of lead deposition on surfaces due to Novel Taser use and conclude that further research is indicated.

1. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Tasers are electroshock weapons that are used as a defense strategy more frequently in law enforcement protocols for assailant take-downs by use of non-lethal force (Thorne, 2023). They work by propelling a small dart from a handgun taser connected by two wires to the taser where electroshock is controlled by a trigger user. The triggered shock by the user disrupts the body’s nervous system, resulting in temporary incapacitation (Plouffe, 2025). Prior research has focused on the

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physiological effects associated with electrical pulsed shock (Baliatsas et al., 2021). Investigators have identified impacts to cognitive function (White et al., 2014), electroencephalogram patterns (Gibbons et al., 2017), respiratory patterns (Ho et al., 2007), pH balance in the blood (Dawes et al., 2010; Ho et al., 2009), and perturbation to metabolic enzyme levels (Dawes et al., 2010). We were not able to find prior published work that investigated the association of taser use and heavy metal exposure. Primers containing lead are used both handgun and rifle ammunition and tasers as well. Primers have been identified as sources of lead exposure at handgun and rifle ranges (Laidlaw et al., 2017).

Lead exposure associated with gun ranges has long been recognized as a major source of lead contamination for law enforcement and military personnel and more recently recreational shooters (Laidlaw et al., 2017). However, lead exposure has been assumed to be associated with handgun or rifle ammunition projectiles and primers (Laidlaw et al., 2017; Raheed, 2021; Scott, Pavechak and DePersis, 2012; Vandebroek et al., 2019). It has been estimated that there are between 16,000 to 18,000 firing ranges in the US. Much concern has been raised for frequent users with higher levels of exposure on the range as well as potentially adverse impacts to the habitat in proximity to the range. The EPA (2005) has published lead management guidelines for shooting ranges to help reduce lead in the environment. While primers have been identified as sources of lead related to handgun and rifle use, no investigation of lead exposure has focused on primers associated with CEWs.

Exposure of greatest concern has been airborne particulates and secondarily surface contamination in range location on equipment furniture and other surfaces (Laidlaw et al., 2017; Rasheed, 2021; Scott, Pavechak and DePersis, 2012; Vandebroek et al., 2019). Laidlaw and Colleagues (2017) looked at 31 studies and found that researchers have identified elevated blood lead levels (BLLs) among shooters ranging from $>10 \mu\text{g/dL}$ to $> 40 \mu\text{g/dL}$. Relationships were identified between the blood lead level and aerosol discharge, gun, number of rounds fired and caliber of round. Rasheed (2021) examined 34 studies that investigated shooter BLLs. He identified research related to both indoor and outdoor environments. The review of studies included 10 in relation military, police and intelligence agencies. It was concluded that protection is maximized by preventing exposure. Given that exposure is almost certain (BLLs) should be monitored. Safety measures should be taken respectively with elevated levels, see Table 1.

Lead sampling at shooting ranges have focused on airborne particles (Alcock, Wajak & Oosthuizen, 2022) and in the soils (Hardison et al., 2004). Alcock and colleagues (2022) evaluated both airborne and surface contamination of lead in a newly commissioned indoor range to assess the effectiveness of the ventilation system to reduce contamination and exposure to shooters. The research team obtained air samples from eight shooters using personal IOM samplers placed on the breathing zone of the shooters and seven environmental samples placed 1.5 meters above ground in strategic location where contamination was expected (Alcock, Wajak & Oosthuizen, 2022). The investigators also collected surface wipe samples following NIOSH Method 9100. Their findings revealed airborne concentrations ranging between 0.078 mg/m^3 to 0.163 mg/m^3 from personal samplers in the breathing zone. Environmental monitoring revealed concentrations ranging from 22 to 40 mg/m^3 throughout the range. The surface wipe samples revealed concentrations ranging from $0.02 \mu\text{g/cm}^2$ to $38.377 \mu\text{g/cm}^2$ from 17 locations throughout the range (Alcock, Wajak & Oosthuizen, 2022). The research team concluded that ranges continue to be significant sources of lead exposure and good housekeeping practices are essential. The team reported acceptable levels of surface dust contamination has been published in Australia, see Table 2.

Table 1

The BLL of occupationally exposed workers and required safety measures, January 2020

BLL value (µg/dL)	Safety decision	Health and safety measures
Case definition range		
BLL (0.1µg/dL - 0.49µg/dL)	Case definition for BLL though "no safe value"	Check BLL monthly for 3 months to ensure 0.00µg/dL level is achieved.
BLL (0.5µg/dL – 1.49µg/dL)	-Remove pregnant women from lead exposure or women in reproductive age. -Evaluate workplace lead exposure, available controls and safety measures.	Check BLL monthly for 3 months, then every 3 months until the value of 0.00µg/dL - 0.01µg/dL level is achieved.
Range that call for caution		
BLL (1.5µg/dL – 1.99µg/dL)	-Implement workplace changes to reduce exposure to lead. -Inform workers of the health implication of high BLL. -Evaluate sources of excessive exposure to lead, and identify ineffective work safety measures.	Check BLL monthly and ensure value of 0.00µg/dL- 0.01µg/dL is achieved
Range dangerous to health		
BLL (2.0µg/dL – 2.49µg/dL)	-Is mandatory to inform worker of the health implication of BLL. -Remove worker from lead pollutants and apply medical treatment until BLL returns to acceptable level. -Enhance safety measures to reduce exposure to lead using administrative and engineering controls to ensure safe practices.	Check BLL monthly until the value of 0.00µg/dL- 0.01µg/dL is achieved
Range that signify lead toxicity		
BLL ≥ 5.0µg/dL	-inform affected workers about their current BLL level. -Remove worker from lead exposure and commence medical treatment to return the BLL to acceptable level. -Notify medical director. -Identify sources of lead exposure at workplace and implement corrective actions to reduce or stop the exposure. -Control measures at workplace must be implemented to reduce exposure.	Check the BLL monthly until the value of 0.00µg/dL- 0.01µg/dL is achieved

Note: Table 1. Designed from the reviewed literature of ABLES/CDC/NIOSH, 2015. µg/dL = microgram per deciliter.

Source: Rasheed, T. (2021). Occupational Lead Exposure and Safety Measures at Shooting Ranges: A Systematic Review. *Archives of Occupational Health*, 5(3), 1084-1091.

Table 2

Acceptable surface dust lead loadings [18]

Location	Lead Loading	Unit
Interior floors	0.1	µg/cm ²
Interior windowsills	0.5	µg/cm ²
Exterior Surfaces	0.8	µg/cm ²

Source: Alcock, R., Wajrak, M., & Oosthuizen, J. (2022). Assessment of the effectiveness of ventilation controls in managing airborne and surface lead levels at a newly commissioned indoor shooting range. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(18), 11711.

This pilot study was designed to investigate the potential of lead exposure directly associated with the Novel Taser. The hypothesis was that lead would be present on surfaces within the non-range locations due to Novel Taser use. Investigation strategies were developed to identify and evaluation lead contamination on various surfaces within the training facility.

2. METHODS

A partnership existed between the local health department and a police training facility in Colorado. To study concentrations of heavy metal distribution using a Taser 10 model, a replicate study was conducted on January 29, 2025 at a law enforcement training facility in Colorado. The training center has grappling mats, a weight room, two bathrooms and an office with normal commercial ventilation. The trainers fired approximately 90 rounds to simulate training day conditions. Lead surface samples were taken following NIOSH Method 9100 from various objects within the training center. Wipe Sampling was performed in designated locations where cadets would be grappling and also firing the tasers. These samples designated an area of one foot squared and were taken with the “S” sampling method and analyzed as discrete samples per area. Samples were submitted to Eurofins in Denver Colorado, an accredited National Environmental Laboratory Accreditation Program with Eurofins Reservoirs is an analytical laboratory also accredited for the analysis of Industrial Hygiene and Environmental matrices by the American Industrial Hygiene Association (AIHA LAP, LLC), Lab ID 101533 (Eurofins, 2024).

3. RESULTS

Wipe samples taken in three locations in the training center. Findings revealed levels ranged from a low of 7 µg/ft² on a grappling mat to a high of 47 µg/ft² on one trainer keyboard, see Table 3.

Table 3

Wipe Results for Lead on Surfaces

LOCATION	Concentration µg/ft ² (µg/cm ²)
Grappling mat control	28.9 (0.0311077 µg/cm ²)
Grappling mat after firing	7.0 (0.00554737 µg/cm ²)
Trainer 1 keyboard	47.0 (0.050590377 µg/cm ²)
Trainer 2 keyboard	BRL*

**BRL- Below Reportable Limits*

4. DISCUSSION

This pilot study was carried out in a law enforcement training center in Colorado to evaluate the need for more sampling and research. To that end, our findings suggest that additional sampling is needed. We also feel that future sampling should include additional surfaces and air samples as well. The investigation did not find levels of lead above recommended levels set by prior authorities for dust in shooting environment (Alcock, Wajrak & Oosthuizen, 2022). Although samples were not taken from windowsills and floors but did include grappling mats placed on the floors and thus standards are applicable. The recommend level for safe lead dust exposure is 0.1 µg/cm². The NIOSH method 9100 recommends sampling with wipes per ft². We found a concentration of lead at 7 µg/ft² after firing the Novel Taser, to convert this concentration to the units in the Australian standard we used the following equation $7 \times 0.00107639104 = 0.007534737 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$. On the control mat we found a concentration of 28.9 µg/ft² we converted this following the same formula $28.9 \times 0.00107639104 = 0.0311077 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$.

The highest concentration was seen on the computer keyboard $47 \mu\text{g}/\text{ft}^2$. Converting the concentration, we use the same formula: $47 \mu\text{g}/\text{ft}^2 \times 0.00107639104 = 0.050590377 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$.

All three samples were below the Australian lead dust standard. However, there is no safe level of exposure to lead (Gundacker et al., 2021; WHO, 2023). Lead toxicity can adversely affect multiple systems including: Nervous, renal, cardiovascular, hematological, immunological, reproductive, and developmental (ATSDR, 2020). Further work is needed to adequately evaluate sources of lead from CEWs in law enforcement. It is clear that law enforcement and military personnel are at risk for exposure and lead toxicity. There exists BLL data suggesting lead exposure is associated shooting traditional weapons. Blood samples obtained from law enforcement personnel from 2006 through 2009 revealed the average BLL at $24.2 \mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$ in that primary population (Scott, Pavelichak & DePersis, 2012). The CDC (2021) established thresholds for lead cases at $10 \mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$ for adults and $3.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$ for children (CDC, 2025). Recreational shooters have also been studied and found to have significantly lower BLLs compared to law enforcement, the average concentration was found to be less than $2 \mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$ (Scott, Pavelichak & DePersis, 2012). It is not known what proportion of lead exposure is associated with CEWs. Further research is needed.

Housekeeping in lead environments such as ranges is important for reducing exposure to particulates from ammunition and all types of lead containing primers (Alcock, Wajrak & Oosthuizen, 2022; Scott, Pavelichak & DePersis, 2012) including CEWs. Scott and colleagues (2012) examined an indoor range using both air and wipe samples for the detection of lead. Significant TWA were seen ranging from a low of $26 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to a high of $350 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ with an overall average of $121.4 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Wipe samples also revealed significant surface contamination with concentrations ranging from $< 5 \mu\text{g}/\text{ft}^2$ to a high of $132,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{ft}^2$ on a bracket inside the shooting range with an overall average of $14,709 \mu\text{g}/\text{ft}^2$. Authors concluded that measures were needed to reduce potential exposure including ventilation, lead free primers and effective housekeeping cleaning activities (Scott, Pavelichak & DePersis, 2012).

Several limitations in this pilot study are recognized and include the small sample size. This was an exploratory study only, findings do not represent all training facilities. Future work should include a larger sample size. Also, wipe sampling on this day were performed under abnormal conditions and were simulated to be like taser training day. This simulation may not accurately represent the actual exposure during training. The sampling was done to test whether the Taser 10 cartridge created a lead hazard to cadets or trainers. We suggest that more research is needed to answer this question. Our findings do not suggest immediate lead hazards exist with the number of taser firings.

Additionally, the trainers fired close to 90 rounds to simulate training day where around 100 rounds are fired. The highest level of lead was found on a trainer's keyboard at $47.0 \mu\text{g}/\text{ft}^2$. The other detectable levels of lead were found on the grappling mats with three samples having $28.9 \mu\text{g}/\text{ft}^2$, $7.0 \mu\text{g}/\text{ft}^2$ and $1.9 \mu\text{g}/\text{ft}^2$. Since there was detectable lead on one trainer's keyboard and on the grappling mats, it is plausible that the lead would be from the cartridges. Although the Novel Taser cartridges may create a lead hazard, it must be noted that there are also other lead hazards known in this area where there is also a shooting range on-site.

Finally, the trainers at this facility do not train with firearms for the cadet academy but they may share keyboards with other shooting range trainers. Dust and soil may also be tracked from the range to the grappling mats inside of the grappling center. This is likely but, the shooting range is more than 1,000 yards away from the area that we examined. There is potential in this case for contamination from the

shooting range to be tracked in on shoes, clothing or hands and more study needs to be performed to categorize the risk of Novel Tasers and heavy metals.

The exposure to taser primers is directly associated with the training process. Typically, the cadet will fire a taser and a training officer will certify that the cadet has correctly fired a taser for the academy module. In essence, these modules are a one-day event, and every cadet will be certified this day so the exposure by the lead primer is most likely to occur during this scenario. The training schedule increases frequency of exposure to inhalable aerosol primer and for increased distribution of the particulate aerosol substance on surfaces, grapple mats, office equipment, and trainers' field equipment.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

There needs to be further occupational study in indoor and outdoor firing ranges or other training facilities which use Novel Tasers. Some taser training for cadets and other specialized users occurs during module style academy training where the length ranges from 16 to 40 weeks (C.P.O.S.T., 2025). This means that the taser module is designated and exclusively timed in the cadet training. Trainers and management need to be aware of the limitations in their ventilation system and practice good housekeeping with regular cleaning of surfaces such as grappling mats and keyboard where contact is certain. There should be a particulate filtering ventilation system to capture firearm and CEW discharged lead particulates in the air. There should also be proper hygiene with cleaning solutions designed for lead cleaning then the lead in aerosol or lead on surfaces could become an exposure. Since many law enforcement officers are part of government entities like municipal or county level structures, they are exempt from OSHA and there may be more exposure risk from indoor and outdoor gun ranges on site than by Novel Tasers (O.S.H.A., US).

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

Mrs. Kayla Lesparence was the graduate student who conceived the project and worked in all phases of the study and manuscript preparation. Mrs. Lesparence defended her work and graduated and now is recognized as a Graduate Safety Professional (GSP) and practicing Industrial Hygienist. Kayla earned her bachelor's degree in Environmental Health at Colorado State University and her master's in IH at Montana Tech University. Dr. Birkenbuel is an Associate Professor who provided support for the project and review for this manuscript. Dr. Gilkey was the Co-Major Advisor who worked with Kayla through all phases of the project.

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